

34.375% (33.72%)-Maximal Efficiencies, obtained in CdSe_{1-x}S_x, CdSe_{1-x}Te_x-Crystalline Alloy Junction Solar Cells at 300 K

Huynh Van Cong ✉

Université de Perpignan Via Domitia, Laboratoire de Mathématiques
et Physique (LAMPS), EA 4217, Département de Physique, 52, Avenue Paul Alduy,
F-66 860 Perpignan, France

ABSTRACT:

In two new single $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ X(x)-alloy junction solar cells at 300 K, [X(x)≡ CdSe_{1-x}S_x, CdSe_{1-x}Te_x], $0 \leq x \leq 1$, by basing on the same physical model-and-treatment method, as used in our recent works [1, 2], and also other works [3-6], some important results, obtained in the present work, are reported in the following.

As noted in Tables 2.1, 3.1, 4.1 and 5.1, the dark carrier-minority saturation current density $J_{ol(oII)}$ decreases slightly with increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -radius for given x, and decreases strongly with increasing x, for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius. Further, as discussed in Eq. (45), at a same V_{oc} , both $J_{ol(oII)}$ and $n_{I(I)}$ have the same variations for same physical conditions.

In particular, at x=0 and for Sn^+Cd (Cd^+Sn), both $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ CdSe_{1-x}S_x(Te_x) [≡ CdSe] alloys become CdSe-crystals, as observed in Tables 1.1 and 1.2, and therefore, as given in Tables 2.2 (3.2), and 4.2 (5.2), we get the same numerical results of $\eta_{I_{max.}(II_{max.})}$ [=28.184 % (28.310 %)].

Further, at x=1 and for Sn^+Cd (Cd^+Sn), we obtain: (a) in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ CdSe_{1-x}S_x [≡ CdS] alloy-junction solar cells, $\eta_{I_{max.}(II_{max.})}$ =34.375 % (33.72 %) and T_H =457.1 K (452.6 K), as those given in Tables 2.2 (3.2), and (b) in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ CdSe_{1-x}Te_x [≡ CdTe] alloy-junction solar cells, $\eta_{I_{max.}(II_{max.})}$ =25.676 % (25.443 %), according to: T_H =403.6 K (402.4 K), respectively, as those given in Tables 4.2 (5.2).

Finally, from above remarks, we could conclude that, in order to obtain the highest efficiencies, the present (CdSe_{1-x}S_x, CdSe_{1-x}Te_x)- crystalline alloy junction solar cells could be chosen rather than the crystalline (CdSe, CdTe)-junction solar cells [1, 2], yielding the highest efficiencies equal to: 26.55 % and 23.69 %, respectively.

Keywords: (CdS_{1-x}Se_x, CdS_{1-x}Te_x)-crystalline alloy junction solar cells, single crystalline CdTe-junction solar cell, photovoltaic conversion factor, photovoltaic conversion efficiency.

Suggested Citation: H. Van Cong, " 34.375% (33.72%)-Maximal Efficiencies, obtained in CdSe_{1-x}S_x, CdSe_{1-x}Te_x-Crystalline Alloy Junction Solar Cells at 300 K," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 2(2), pp. 150-174, Mar-Apr 2024. DOI: [10.59324/ejaset.2024.2\(2\).11](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejaset.2024.2(2).11)

INTRODUCTION

In two new single $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ X(x)-alloy junction solar cells at 300 K, [X(x)≡ CdSe_{1-x}S_x, CdSe_{1-x}Te_x], $0 \leq x \leq 1$, by basing on the same physical model-and-treatment method, as used in our recent works [1, 2], and also other works [3-11], some important results, obtained in the present work, are reported in the following.

(i)-As noted in Tables 2.1, 3.1, 4.1 and 5.1, the dark carrier-minority saturation current density $J_{ol(oII)}$ decreases slightly with increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -radius for given x, and decreases strongly with increasing x,

for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius. Then, as remarked in Tables 2.2, 3.2, 4.2 and 5.2, at a same V_{oc} , the photovoltaic conversion factor, $n_{I(II)}(V_{oc})$, decreases slightly with increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -radius for given x , but it decreases strongly with increasing x , for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius. In other words, as discussed in Eq. (45), at a same V_{oc} , both $J_{oI(oII)}$ and $n_{I(II)}$ have the same variations for same physical conditions.

(ii)-With such variations of $n_{I(II)}(V_{oc})$, as observed in Tables 2.2, 3.2, 4.2 and 5.2, the maximal values of $\eta_{I(II)}$, $\eta_{I(II)max.}$ and the corresponding ones of the H-reservoir temperature, T_H , are obtained at $V_{oc} = V_{ocI(oCII)}$, being marked in bold, increase with increasing x for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius.

(iii)-In particular, at $x=0$, both $n^+(p^+) - p(n) CdSe_{1-x}S_x(Te_x)[\equiv CdSe]$ alloys become the CdSe-crystal, as observed in Tables 1.1 and 1.2, and therefore, as given in Tables 2.2, 3.2, 4.2, and 5.2, we get the same numerical results of $\eta_{I(max.)(II max.)} [=28.184 \% (28.310 \%)]$.

(iv)-Further, at $x=1$ and for $Sn^+Cd (Cd^+Sn)$, we obtain: (a) in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n) CdSe_{1-x}S_x[\equiv CdS]$ alloy-junction solar cells, $\eta_{I(max.)(II max.)} = 34.375 \% (33.72 \%)$ and $T_H = 457.1 K (452.6 K)$, as those given in Tables 2.2 (3.2), and (b) in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n) CdSe_{1-x}Te_x[\equiv CdTe]$ alloy-junction solar cells, $\eta_{I(max.)(II max.)} = 25.676 \% (25.443 \%)$, according to: $T_H = 403.6 K (402.4 K)$, respectively, as those given in Tables 4.2 (5.2).

Furthermore, from above remarks (iii) and (iv), we can conclude that in order to obtain the highest efficiencies, the present $(CdSe_{1-x}S_x, CdSe_{1-x}Te_x)$ - crystalline alloy junction solar cells could be chosen rather than the crystalline $(CdSe, CdTe)$ -junction solar cells [1, 2], yielding the highest efficiencies equal to: 26.55 % and 23.69 %, respectively.

In the following, the energy band structure parameters and the dark minority-carrier saturation current density, due to the effects of x - concentration, impurity size, and heavy doping, the photovoltaic effect, and finally some numerical results and concluding remarks will be investigated.

ENERGY BAND STRUCTURE PARAMETERS AND DARK MINORITY-CARRIER SATURATION CURRENT DENSITY

First of all, in two $n^+(p^+) - p(n) X(x)(\equiv CdSe_{1-x}S_x, CdSe_{1-x}Te_x)$ - crystalline alloy junction solar cells, we present the effects of x -concentration on such $X(x)$ -alloy, donor (acceptor) $[d(a)]$ -size, temperature T and heavy doping, affecting strongly the energy-band-structure parameters [1, 2], in order to investigate the total minority-carrier saturation current densities, as those given in the following.

A. Effects of x -concentration on such $X(x)$ - alloy

In the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ single $n^+(p^+) - p(n) X(x)$ - alloy junction at $T=0 K$, the intrinsic energy-band-structure parameters such as: the effective average number of equivalent conduction (valence)-band edges $g_{c(v)}(x)$, the unperturbed relative effective electron (hole) mass in conduction (valence) bands $m_{c(v)}(x)/m_0$, m_0 being the electron rest mass, the unperturbed relative dielectric constant $\epsilon_0(x)$, expressed as functions of x , are given in the following.

(i)-The unperturbed relative effective electron (hole) mass in conduction (valence) bands are given by [1, 2]:

$$m_c(x)/m_0 = [m_{c(CdS)}/m_0]([m_{c(CdTe)}/m_0]) \times x + [m_{c(CdSe)}/m_0] \times (1 - x), \text{ and}$$

$$m_v(x)/m_0 = [m_{v(CdS)}/m_0]([m_{v(CdTe)}/m_0]) \times x + [m_{v(CdSe)}/m_0] \times (1 - x), \quad (1)$$

for the $[CdSe_{1-x}S_x]([CdSe_{1-x}Te_x])$ - alloy, respectively.

Here, one has: $m_{c(CdS)}/m_0=0.197$, $m_{c(CdSe)}/m_0=0.11$, $m_{c(CdTe)}/m_0=0.095$, $m_{v(CdS)}/m_0=0.801$, $m_{v(CdSe)}/m_0=0.45$, and $m_{v(CdTe)}/m_0=0.82$.

(ii)-The unperturbed relative dielectric constant of the intrinsic of the single crystalline X- alloy is found to be defined by [1, 2]:

$$\epsilon_o(x) = \epsilon_{CdS} (\epsilon_{CdTe}) \times x + \epsilon_{CdSe} \times (1 - x). \quad (2)$$

Here, one has: $\epsilon_{CdS} = 9$, $\epsilon_{CdSe} = 10.2$, and $\epsilon_{CdTe} = 10.31$.

(iii)-Finally, the unperturbed band gap is found to be given by [1, 2]:

$$E_{go}(x) \text{ in eV} = E_{gCdS}(x) [E_{gCdTe}(x)] \times x + E_{gCdSe}(x) \times (1 - x), \quad (3)$$

where $E_{gCdS}(x) = 2.58$ eV, $E_{gCdSe}(x) = 1.84$ eV, and $E_{gCdTe}(x) = 1.62$ eV.

Therefore, we can define the effective donor (acceptor)-ionization energy at $r_{d(a)} = r_{do(ao)} = r_{Se(Cd)} = 0.114$ nm (0.148 nm), in absolute values, as [1, 2]:

$$E_{do(ao)}(x) = \frac{13600 \times [m_c(v)(x)/m_o]}{[\epsilon_o(x)]^2} \text{ meV}, \quad (4)$$

and then, the isothermal bulk modulus, by:

$$B_{do(ao)}(x) \equiv \frac{E_{do(ao)}(x)}{(4\pi/3) \times (r_{do(ao)})^3}. \quad (5)$$

B. Effects of Impurity-size, with a given x

Here, due to the effects of $r_{d(a)}$ and x- concentration, all the energy-band-structure parameters will be expressed in terms of the effective relative static dielectric constant, $\epsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)$, as follows.

At $r_{d(a)} = r_{do(ao)} = r_{Se(Cd)} = 0.114$ nm (0.148 nm), respectively, the needed boundary conditions are found to be: for the impurity-atom volume $V = (4\pi/3) \times (r_{d(a)})^3$, $V_{do(ao)} = (4\pi/3) \times (r_{do(ao)})^3$, for the pressure p , $p_o = 0$, and for the deformation potential energy (or the strain energy) σ , $\sigma_o = 0$. Further, the two important equations [1, 2, 6, 7], needed to determine the σ -variation $\Delta\sigma \equiv \sigma - \sigma_o = \sigma$, are defined by: $\frac{dp}{dV} = -\frac{B}{V}$ and $p = -\frac{d\sigma}{dV}$. giving: $\frac{d}{dV}(\frac{d\sigma}{dV}) = \frac{B}{V}$. Then, by an integration, one gets:

$$\begin{aligned} [\Delta\sigma(r_{d(a)}, x)]_{d(a)} &= B_{do(ao)}(x) \times (V - V_{do(ao)}) \times \ln\left(\frac{V}{V_{do(ao)}}\right) = \\ &= E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}}\right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}}\right)^3. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Furthermore, by using the effective Bohr model, we also shown [1, 2, 3, 4, 5] that, as $r_{d(a)} > r_{do(ao)}$ ($r_{d(a)} < r_{do(ao)}$), the compression (dilatation), being represented by: $\pm [\Delta\sigma(r_{d(a)}, x)]_{n(p)}$, increases (decreases) the energy gap $E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, and the effective donor (acceptor)-ionization energy $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ in absolute values, as:

for $r_{d(a)} \geq r_{do(ao)}$,

$$E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{go}(x) = E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{do(ao)}(x) = E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\varepsilon(r_{d(a)})} \right)^2 - 1 \right] = + [\Delta\sigma(r_{d(a)}, x)]_{n(p)},$$

and for $r_{d(a)} \leq r_{do(ao)}$,

$$E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{go}(x) = E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{do(ao)}(x) = E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\varepsilon(r_{d(a)})} \right)^2 - 1 \right] = - [\Delta\sigma(r_{d(a)}, x)]_{n(p)}. \quad (7)$$

Therefore, from Equations 6 and 7, one obtains the expressions for relative dielectric constant $\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and energy band gap $E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, as:

$$(i)\text{-for } r_{d(a)} \geq r_{do(ao)}, \text{ since } \varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x) = \frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\sqrt{1 + \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3}} \leq \varepsilon_o(x),$$

$$E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{go}(x) = E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{do(ao)}(x) = E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 \geq 0, \quad (8a)$$

according to the increase in both $E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, for a given x , and

$$(ii)\text{-for } r_{d(a)} \leq r_{do(ao)}, \text{ since } \varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x) = \frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\sqrt{1 - \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3}} \geq \varepsilon_o(x), \text{ with a condition, given by:}$$

$$\left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 < 1,$$

$$E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{go}(x) = E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - E_{do(ao)}(x) = -E_{do(ao)}(x) \times \left[\left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 - 1 \right] \times \ln \left(\frac{r_{d(a)}}{r_{do(ao)}} \right)^3 \leq 0, \quad (8.b)$$

corresponding to the decrease in both $E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, for a given x .

C. Effect of T, with given x and $r_{d(a)}$

Here, as given in our previous works [1, 2], the intrinsic band gap $E_{gin(gip)}(r_{d(a)}, x, T)$ is given by:

$$E_{gin(gip)}(r_{d(a)}, x, T) \text{ in eV} = E_{gn(gp)}(r_{d(a)}, x) - \frac{10^{-4} \times T^2}{T + 94 \text{ K}} \times \{7.0043 \times x + 4.3779 \times (1 - x)\}, \quad (9)$$

which decreases, for given x and $r_{d(a)}$, with an increasing T .

Furthermore, in the n(p)-type X(x)-alloy, one can define the intrinsic carrier concentration $n_{in(ip)}$ by:

$$n_{in(p)}^2(T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv N_c(T, x) \times N_v(T, x) \times \exp\left(\frac{-E_{gin(p)}(T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{k_B T}\right), \quad (10)$$

where $N_{c(v)}(T, x)$ is the conduction (valence)-band density of states, being defined as:

$$N_{c(v)}(T, x) = 2 \times \left(\frac{m_{c(v)}(x) \times k_B T}{2\pi\hbar^2}\right)^{\frac{3}{2}} \text{ (cm}^{-3}\text{)}. \quad (11)$$

So, the numerical results of $E_{d(a)}(r_{d(a)}, x)$, $B_{do(ao)}(x)$, $\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)$ and $E_{gin(gip)}(r_{d(a)}, x, T)$, calculated using Equations (4), (5), (8a), (8b) and (9), are reported in following Tables 1.1 and 1.2 in Appendix 1.

Tables 1.1 and 1.2 in Appendix 1

D. Heavy Doping Effect, with given T, x and $r_{d(a)}$

Here, as given in our previous works [3, 4, 5], the Fermi energy $E_{Fn}(-E_{Fp})$, band gap narrowing (BGN), and apparent band gap narrowing (ABGN), are reported in the following.

First, the Fermi energy $E_{Fn}(-E_{Fp})$, obtained for any T and any d(a)-density, $N_{d(a)}$, being investigated in our previous paper [3, 4, 5], with a precision of the order of 2.11×10^{-4} , is found to be given by:

$$\frac{E_{Fn}(u)}{k_B T} \left(\frac{-E_{Fp}(u)}{k_B T}\right) = \frac{G(u) + Au^B F(u)}{1 + Au^B}, \quad A = 0.0005372 \text{ and } B = 4.82842262, \quad (12)$$

where u is the reduced electron density, $u(N_{d(a)}, T, x) \equiv \frac{N_{d(a)}}{N_{c(v)}(T, x)}$, $F(u) = au^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(1 + bu^{-\frac{4}{3}} + cu^{-\frac{8}{3}}\right)^{-\frac{2}{3}}$, $a = \left[(3\sqrt{\pi}/4) \times u\right]^{2/3}$, $b = \frac{1}{8} \left(\frac{\pi}{a}\right)^2$, $c = \frac{62.3739855}{1920} \left(\frac{\pi}{a}\right)^4$, and $G(u) \simeq \ln(u) + 2^{-\frac{3}{2}} \times u \times e^{-du}$; $d = 2^{3/2} \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{27}} - \frac{3}{16}\right] > 0$.

Here, one notes that: (i) as $u \gg 1$, according to the HD [d(a)-X(x)- alloy] ER-case, or to the degenerate one, Eq. (12) is reduced to the function $F(u)$, and (ii) $\frac{E_{Fn}(u \ll 1)}{k_B T} \left(\frac{-E_{Fp}(u \ll 1)}{k_B T}\right) \ll -1$, to the LD [a(d)- X(x)- alloy] BR-case, or to the non-degenerate one, Eq. (12) is reduced to the function $G(u)$.

Secondly, if denoting the effective Wigner-Seitz radius $r_{sn(sp)}$, characteristic of the interactions, by:

$$r_{sn(sp)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, x) = 1.1723 \times 10^8 \times \left(\frac{g_{c(v)}}{N_{d(a)}}\right)^{1/3} \times \frac{m_{c(v)}(x)}{\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)}, \quad g_{c(v)} = 1(1), \quad (13)$$

the correlation energy of an effective electron gas, $E_{cn(cp)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, x)$, is given as [6, 7]:

$$E_{cn(cp)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, x) = \frac{-0.87553}{0.0908 + r_{sn(sp)}} + \frac{\frac{0.87553}{0.0908 + r_{sn(sp)}} + \left(\frac{2[1 - \ln(2)]}{\pi^2}\right) \times \ln(r_{sn(sp)}) - 0.093288}{1 + 0.03847728 \times r_{sn(sp)}^{1.67378876}}.$$

Now, taking into account various spin-polarized chemical potential-energy contributions such as [6, 7]: exchange energy of an effective electron (hole) gas, majority-carrier correlation energy of an

effective electron (hole) gas, minority hole (electron) correlation energy, majority electron (hole)-ionized d(a) interaction screened Coulomb potential energy, and finally minority hole (electron)-ionized d(a) interaction screened Coulomb potential energy, the band gap narrowing (BGN) are given as follows.

Then, in the n-type HD $X(x)$ - alloy, the BGN is found to be given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E_{gn}(N_d, r_d, x) \simeq & a_1 \times \frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\varepsilon(r_d, x)} \times N_r^{\frac{1}{3}} + a_2 \times \frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\varepsilon(r_d, x)} \times N_r^{\frac{1}{3}} \times (2.503 \times [-E_{cn}(r_{sn}) \times r_{sn}]) + a_3 \times \\ & \times \left[\frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\varepsilon(r_d, x)} \right]^{\frac{5}{4}} \times \sqrt{\frac{m_v}{m_c}} \times N_r^{\frac{1}{4}} + a_4 \times \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\varepsilon(r_d, x)}} \times N_r^{\frac{1}{2}} \times \\ & \times 2 + a_5 \times \left[\frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\varepsilon(r_d, x)} \right]^{\frac{3}{2}} \times N_r^{\frac{1}{6}}, \quad N_r \equiv \left(\frac{N_d}{9.999 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (14n)$$

where $a_1 = 3.8 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$, $a_2 = 6.5 \times 10^{-4}(\text{eV})$, $a_3 = 2.8 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$, $a_4 = 5.597 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$ and $a_5 = 8.1 \times 10^{-4}(\text{eV})$, and in the p-type HD $X(x)$ - alloy, as:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E_{gp}(N_a, r_a, x) \simeq & a_1 \times \frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\varepsilon(r_a, x)} \times N_r^{\frac{1}{3}} + a_2 \times \frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\varepsilon(r_a, x)} \times N_r^{\frac{1}{3}} \times (2.503 \times [-E_{cp}(r_{sp}) \times r_{sp}]) + a_3 \times \\ & \times \left[\frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\varepsilon(r_a, x)} \right]^{\frac{5}{4}} \times \sqrt{\frac{m_c}{m_v}} \times N_r^{\frac{1}{4}} + 2a_4 \times \sqrt{\frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\varepsilon(r_a, x)}} \times N_r^{\frac{1}{2}} + \\ & + a_5 \times \left[\frac{\varepsilon_o(x)}{\varepsilon(r_a, x)} \right]^{\frac{3}{2}} \times N_r^{\frac{1}{6}}, \quad N_r \equiv \left(\frac{N_a}{9.999 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (14p)$$

where $a_1 = 3.15 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$, $a_2 = 5.41 \times 10^{-4}(\text{eV})$, $a_3 = 2.32 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$, $a_4 = 4.195 \times 10^{-3}(\text{eV})$ and $a_5 = 9.80 \times 10^{-5}(\text{eV})$.

Therefore, in the HD[d(a)- $X(x)$ - alloy] ER, we can define the effective extrinsic carrier concentration, $n_{en(ep)}^*$, by :

$$n_{en(ep)}^*(N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \sqrt{N_{d(a)} \times p_o(n_o)} = n_{in(ip)}(T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times \exp \left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(aggp)}}{2k_B T} \right], \quad (15)$$

where the apparent band gap narrowing (ABGN), $\Delta E_{agn(aggp)}$, is defined by:

$$\Delta E_{agn}(N_d, T, r_d, x) \equiv \Delta E_{gn}(N_d, r_d, x) + k_B T \times \ln \left(\frac{N_d}{N_c(T, x)} \right) - E_{Fn}(N_d, T, x), \quad (16n)$$

$$\Delta E_{aggp}(N_a, T, r_a, x) \equiv \Delta E_{gp}(N_a, r_a, x) + k_B T \times \ln \left(\frac{N_a}{N_v(T, x)} \right) + E_{Fp}(N_a, T, x). \quad (16p)$$

E. Total minority-carrier saturation current density

In the two $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ $X(x)$ - alloy -junction solar cells, denoted respectively by I(II), the total carrier-minority saturation current density is defined by:

$$J_{oI(oII)} \equiv J_{Eno(Epo)} + J_{Bpo(Bno)} \quad (17)$$

where $J_{Bpo(Bno)}$ is the minority-electron (hole) saturation current density injected into the LD[a(d)- $X(x)$ - alloy] BR, and $J_{Eno(Epo)}$ is the minority-hole (electron) saturation-current density injected into the HD[d(a)- $X(x)$ - alloy] ER.

$J_{Bpo(Bno)}$ in the LD[a(d)- $X(x)$ - alloy]BR

Here, $J_{Bpo(Bno)}$ is determined by [1, 2]:

$$J_{Bpo(Bno)}(N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x) = \frac{e \times n_{ip(in)}^2(T, r_{a(d)}, x) \times \sqrt{\frac{D_{e(h)}(N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x)}{\tau_{eB(hB)}(N_{a(d)})}}}{N_{a(d)}}, \quad (18)$$

where $n_{ip(in)}^2(T, r_{a(d)}, x)$ is determined Eq. (10), $D_{e(h)}(N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x)$ is the minority electron (minority hole) diffusion coefficient:

$$D_e(N_a, T, r_a, x) = \frac{k_B T}{e} \times \left[850 + \frac{5750}{1 + \left(\frac{N_a}{8 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}}\right)^{1.8}} \right] \times \left(\frac{\epsilon(r_a, x)}{\epsilon_o(x)}\right)^2 \text{ (cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}\text{)}, \quad (19a)$$

$$D_h(N_d, T, r_d, x) = \frac{k_B T}{e} \times \left[85 + \frac{1165}{1 + \left(\frac{N_d}{4 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}}\right)^{0.44}} \right] \times \left(\frac{\epsilon(r_d, x)}{\epsilon_o(x)}\right)^2 \text{ (cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}\text{)}, \quad (19b)$$

and $\tau_{eB(hB)}(N_{a(d)})$ is the minority electron (minority hole) lifetime in the BR:

$$\tau_{eB}(N_a)^{-1} = \frac{1}{10^{-7}} + 3 \times 10^{-13} \times N_a + 1.83 \times 10^{-31} \times N_a^2, \quad (20a)$$

$$\tau_{hB}(N_d)^{-1} = \frac{1}{10^{-7}} + 11.76 \times 10^{-13} \times N_d + 2.78 \times 10^{-31} \times N_d^2. \quad (20b)$$

$J_{Eno(Epo)}$ in the HD[d(a)- $X(x)$ - alloy]ER

In the non-uniformly and heavily doped emitter region of d(a)- $X(x)$ devices, the effective Gaussian d(a)-density profile or the d(a) (majority-e(h)) density, is defined in such the HD[d(a)- $X(x)$ alloy] ER-width W , as [1, 2]:

$$\rho_{d(a)}(y, N_{d(a)}, W) = N_{d(a)} \times \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{y}{W}\right)^2 \times \ln\left[\frac{N_{d(a)}}{N_{do(ao)}(W)}\right]\right\} \equiv N_{d(a)} \times \left[\frac{N_{d(a)}}{N_{do(ao)}(W)}\right]^{-\left(\frac{y}{W}\right)^2}, \quad 0 \leq y \leq W$$

$$N_{do(ao)}(W) \equiv 7.9 \times 10^{17} (2 \times 10^5) \times \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{W}{184.2 (1) \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm}}\right)^{1.066 (0.5)}\right\} \text{ (cm}^{-3}\text{)}, \quad (21)$$

where $\rho_{d(a)}(y=0) = N_{d(a)}$ is the surface d(a)-density, and at the emitter-base junction, $\rho_{d(a)}(y=W) = N_{do(ao)}(W)$, which decreases with increasing W. Further, the “effective doping density” is defined by:

$$N_{d(a)}^*(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \rho_{d(a)}(y) / \exp\left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(agg)}(\rho_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{k_B T}\right],$$

$$N_{d(a)}^*(y=0, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \frac{N_{d(a)}}{\exp\left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(agg)}(N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{k_B T}\right]}, \text{ and}$$

$$N_{d(a)}^*(y=W, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \frac{N_{do(ao)}(W)}{\exp\left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(agg)}(N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{k_B T}\right]}, \quad (22)$$

where the apparent band gap narrowing $\Delta E_{agn(agg)}$ is determined in Eq. (16), replacing $N_{d(a)}$ by $\rho_{d(a)}(y, N_{d(a)}, W)$.

Now, we can define the minority hole (minority electron) transport parameter $F_{h(e)}$ as:

$$F_{h(e)}(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \frac{n_{in(ip)}^2(T, r_{d(a)})}{p_o(n_o) \times D_{h(e)}} = \frac{N_{d(a)}^*}{D_{h(e)}} \equiv \frac{N_{d(a)}}{D_{h(e)}} \times$$

$$\times \left(\frac{n_{in(ip)}}{n_{in(ip)}^*}\right)^2 \equiv \frac{N_{d(a)}}{D_{h(e)} \times \exp\left[\frac{\Delta E_{agn(agg)}}{k_B T}\right]} \quad (cm^{-5} \times s), \quad (23)$$

the minority hole (electron) diffusion length, $L_{h(e)}(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x)$ by:

$$L_{h(e)}^{-2}(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) = [\tau_{hE(eE)} \times D_{h(e)}]^{-1} = (C \times F_{h(e)})^2 = \left(C \times \frac{N_{d(a)}^*}{D_{h(e)}}\right)^2 = \left(C \times \frac{n_{in(ip)}^2(T, r_{d(a)})}{p_o(n_o) \times D_{h(e)}}\right)^2,$$

where the constant C was chosen to be equal to: $2.0893 \times 10^{-30} \text{ (cm}^4/\text{s)}$, and the minority hole (minority electron) lifetime $\tau_{hE(eE)}$ as:

$$\tau_{hE(eE)} \equiv \frac{1}{D_{h(e)} \times L_{h(e)}^{-2}} = \frac{1}{D_{h(e)} \times (C \times F_{h(e)})^2}. \quad (24)$$

Then, under low-level injection, in the absence of external generation, and for the steady-state case, we can define the minority-h(e) density by:

$$p_o(y)[n_o(y)] \equiv \frac{n_{in(ip)}^2}{N_{d(a)}^*(y=W, T, r_{d(a)}, x)}, \quad (25)$$

and a normalized excess minority-h(e) density $u(x)$ or a relative deviation between $p(y)[n(y)]$ and $p_o(y)[n_o(y)]$.

$$u(y) \equiv \frac{p(y)[n(y)] - p_o(y)[n_o(y)]}{p_o(y)[n_o(y)]}, \quad (26)$$

which must verify the two following boundary conditions as:

$$u(y = 0) \equiv \frac{-J_h(y=0)[J_e(y=0)]}{eS \times p_0(y=0)[n_0(y=0)]},$$

$$u(y = W) = \exp\left(\frac{V}{n_{I(I)}(V) \times V_T}\right) - 1.$$

Here, $n_{I(I)}(V)$ is a photovoltaic conversion factor determined latter, $S \left(\frac{cm}{s}\right)$ is the surface recombination velocity at the emitter contact, V is the applied voltage, $V_T \equiv (k_B T/e)$ is the thermal voltage, and the minority-hole (electron) current density $J_{h(e)}(y, r_{d(a)}, x)$.

Further, from the Fick's law for minority hole (electron)-diffusion equations, one has [1, 2]:

$$J_{h(e)}(y, r_{d(a)}, x) = \frac{-e(+e) \times n_{in(ip)}^2}{F_{h(e)}(y)} \times \frac{du(y)}{dy} = \frac{-e(+e)n_{in(ip)}^2 D_{h(e)}(N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, x)}{N_{d(a)}^*(y, r_{d(a)}, x)} \times \frac{du(y)}{dy}, \quad (27)$$

where $N_{d(a)}^*(y, r_{d(a)}, x)$ is given in Eq. (22), $D_{h(e)}$ and $F_{h(e)}$ are determined respectively in Equations (19) and (23), and from the minority-hole (electron) continuity equation as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dJ_{h(e)}(y, r_{d(a)}, x)}{dy} &= -e(+e) \times n_{in(p)}^2 \times \frac{u(y)}{F_{h(e)}(y) \times L_{h(e)}^2(y)} = \\ &= -e(+e) \times n_{in(p)}^2 \times \frac{u(y)}{N_{d(a)}^*(y, r_{d(a)}, x) \times \tau_{hE}(eE)}, \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Therefore, the following second-order differential equation is obtained:

$$\frac{d^2 u(y)}{dy^2} - \frac{dF_{h(e)}(y)}{dy} \times \frac{du(y)}{dy} - \frac{u(y)}{L_{h(e)}^2(y)} = 0, \quad (29)$$

Then, taking into account the two above boundary conditions given in Eq. (22), one thus gets the general solution of this Eq. (29), as:

$$u(y) = \frac{\sinh(P(y)) + I(W, S) \times \cosh(P(y))}{\sinh(P(W)) + I(W, S) \times \cosh(P(W))} \times \left(\exp\left(\frac{V}{n_{I(I)}(V) \times V_T}\right) - 1 \right), \quad (30)$$

where the factor $I(W, S)$ is determined by: $D_{h(e)}(N_d, T, r_{d(a)}, x)$

$$I(T, r_{d(a)}, x, W, S) = \frac{D_{h(e)}(y=W, N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{S \times L_{h(e)}(y=W, N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)}. \quad (31)$$

Further, since $\frac{dP(y)}{dy} \equiv C \times F_{h(e)}(y) = \frac{1}{L_{h(e)}(x)}$, $C = 2.0893 \times 10^{-30} (cm^4/s)$, for the X(x)-alloy, being an empirical parameter, chosen for each crystalline semiconductor, $P(y)$ is thus found to be defined by:

$$P(y) \equiv \int_0^y \frac{dy}{L_{h(e)}(y)}, \quad 0 \leq y \leq W, \quad P(y=W) \equiv \left(\frac{1}{W} \times \int_0^W \frac{dy}{L_{h(e)}(y)} \right) \times W \equiv \frac{W}{L_{h(e)}^*(y)} = \frac{L_{h(e)}(y)}{L_{h(e)}^*(y)} \times \frac{W}{L_{h(e)}(y)}, \quad (32)$$

where $L_{h(e)}^*(y)$ is the effective minority hole (minority electron) diffusion length. Further, the minority-hole (electron) current density injected into the HD[d(a)- X(x) alloy] ER is found to be given by:

$$J_{h(e)}(y, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S, V) = -J_{Eno}(y, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S) [J_{Epo}(y, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)] \times \left(\exp\left(\frac{v}{n_{I(I)}(V) \times V_T}\right) - 1 \right), \quad (33)$$

where $J_{Eno(Epo)}$ is the saturation minority hole (minority electron) current density,

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(y, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S) = \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \frac{\cosh(P(x)) + I(W, S) \times \sinh(P(x))}{\sinh(P(W)) + I(W, S) \times \cosh(P(W))}. \quad (34)$$

In the following, we will denote $P(W)$ and $I(W, S)$ by P and I , for a simplicity. So, Eq. (30) gives:

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(y=0, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S) = \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(y, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \frac{1}{\sinh(P) + I \times \cosh(P)}, \quad (35)$$

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S) = \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(y=W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \frac{\cosh(P) + I \times \sinh(P)}{\sinh(P) + I \times \cosh(P)}, \quad (36)$$

and then,

$$\frac{J_{h(e)}(y=0, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S, V)}{J_{h(e)}(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S, V)} \equiv \frac{J_{Eno(Epo)}(y=0, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)}{J_{Eno(Epo)}(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)} = \frac{1}{\cosh(P) + I \times \sinh(P)}. \quad (37)$$

Now, if defining the effective excess minority-hole (electron) charge storage in the emitter region by:

$Q_{h(e)}^*(y=W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \equiv \int_0^W +e(-e) \times u(y) \times p_o(y) [n_o(y)] \times \frac{\tau_{hE(eE)}(N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{\tau_{hE(eE)}(\rho_{d(a)}(x), T, r_{d(a)}, x)} dy$, and the effective minority hole (minority electron) transit time [htt(ett)] by: $\tau_{htt(ett)}^*(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, r_{d(a)}, x, S) \equiv Q_{h(e)}^*(y=W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) / J_{Eno(Epo)}(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)$, and from Equations (24, 31), one obtains:

$$\frac{\tau_{htt(ett)}^*(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)}{\tau_{hE(eE)}} \equiv 1 - \frac{J_{Eno(Epo)}(y=0, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)}{J_{Eno(Epo)}(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)} = 1 - \frac{1}{\cosh(P) + I \times \sinh(P)}. \quad (38)$$

Now, some important results can be obtained and discussed below.

As $P \ll 1$ (or $W \ll L_{h(e)}$) and $S \rightarrow \infty$, $I \equiv I(W, S) = \frac{D_{h(e)}(N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{S \times L_{h(e)}(N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)} \rightarrow 0$, from Eq. (38), one has: $\frac{\tau_{htt(ett)}^*(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)}{\tau_{hE(eE)}} \rightarrow 0$, suggesting a completely transparent emitter region (CTER)-case, where, from Eq. (36), one obtains:

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(y = W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S \rightarrow \infty) \rightarrow \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(y=W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \frac{1}{P(W)}. \quad (39)$$

Further, as $P \gg 1$ (or $W \gg L_{h(e)}$) and $S \rightarrow 0$, $I \equiv I(y = W, r_{d(a)}, x, S) = \frac{D_{h(e)}(N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)}{S \times L_{h(e)}(N_{do(ao)}(W), T, r_{d(a)}, x)} \rightarrow \infty$, and from Eq. (38) one has: $\frac{\tau_{htt(ett)}^*(y=W, W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S)}{\tau_{hE(eE)}} \rightarrow 1$, suggesting a completely opaque emitter region (COER)-case, where, from Eq. (36), one gets:

$$J_{Eno(Epo)}(y = W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S \rightarrow 0) \rightarrow \frac{en_{in(ip)}^2 \times D_{h(e)}}{N_{d(a)}^*(y=W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x) \times L_{h(e)}} \times \tanh(P). \quad (40)$$

In summary, in the two $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ X(x)-alloy junction solar cells, the dark carrier-minority saturation current density $J_{ol(oII)}$, defined in Eq. (17), is now rewritten as:

$$J_{ol(oII)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}, x) \equiv J_{Eno(Epo)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S) + J_{Bpo(Bno)}(N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x), \quad (41)$$

where $J_{Eno(Epo)}$ and $J_{Bpo(Bno)}$ are determined respectively in Equations (36, 18). Further, the numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{htt(ett)}^*}{\tau_{hE(eE)}}$, $J_{Bpo(Bno)}$, $J_{Eno(Epo)}$, and $J_{ol(oII)}$, calculated using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), as those given in Tables (2.1), (3.1), (4.1), and (5.1) in Appendix 1, respectively.

Tables (2.1), (3.1), (4.1), and (5.1) in Appendix 1

PHOTOVOLTAIC CONVERSION EFFECT AT 300 K

Here, in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ X(x)[$\equiv \text{CdSe}_{1-x}\text{S}_x, \text{CdSe}_{1-x}\text{Te}_x$] -alloy junction solar cells at $T=300$ K, denoted respectively by I(II), and for physical conditions, respectively, as:

$$W = 0.1 \mu\text{m}, N_{d \equiv S(a \equiv \text{Cd})} = 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}, r_{d(a)}, x, S = 100 \left(\frac{\text{cm}}{\text{s}} \right); N_{a \equiv \text{Cd}(d \equiv \text{S})} = 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}, r_{a(d)}, x, \quad (42)$$

we propose, at given open circuit voltages: $V_{ocI1(ocI2)}$ and $V_{ocII1(ocII2)}$, the corresponding data of the short circuit current density $J_{scI(II)}$, in order to formulate our following treatment method of two fix points, as:

at $V_{ocI1(ocI2)} = V_{ocII1(ocII2)} = 0.73 \text{ V} (0.8759 \text{ V})$, at which

$$J_{scI1(scI2)} = J_{scII1(scII2)} = 21.16 \text{ mA/cm}^2 \text{ (30.25 mA/cm}^2\text{)}, \quad (43)$$

noting that these numerical results are given in Ref. [6], in which the authors assumed that the “quality factor n ” is equal to 1.

Now, we define the net current density J at $T=300$ K, obtained for the infinite shunt resistance, and expressed as a function of the applied voltage V , flowing through the $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ $X(x)$ -alloy junction of solar cells, as:

$$J(V) \equiv J_{ph.}(V) - J_{ol(oII)} \times (e^{X_{I(II)}(V)} - 1), \quad X_{I(II)}(V) \equiv \frac{V}{n_{I(II)}(V) \times V_T},$$

$$V_T \equiv \frac{k_B T}{e} = 0.02585 \text{ V}, \quad (44)$$

where the function $n_{I(II)}(V)$ is the photovoltaic conversion factor (PVCF), noting that as $V = V_{oc}$, being the open circuit voltage, $J(V = V_{oc}) = 0$, the photocurrent density is defined by: $J_{ph.}(V = V_{oc}) \equiv J_{scI(scII)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc})$, for $V_{oc} \geq V_{ocI1(ocII1)}$.

Therefore, the photovoltaic conversion effect occurs, according to:

$$J_{scI(scII)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc}) \equiv$$

$$\equiv J_{ol(oII)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x) \times (e^{X_{I(II)}(V_{oc})} - 1), \quad (45)$$

where $n_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) \equiv n_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc})$, and $X_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) \equiv \frac{V_{oc}}{n_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) \times V_T}$.

Here, one remarks that (i) for a given V_{oc} , both $n_{I(II)}$ and $J_{ol(oII)}$ have the same variations, obtained in the same physical conditions, as observed in the following calculation, (ii) the function $(e^{X_{I(II)}(V_{oc})} - 1)$ or the PVCF, $n_{I(II)}$, representing the photovoltaic conversion effect, converts the light, represented by $J_{scI(scII)}$, into the electricity, by $J_{ol(oII)}$, and finally, for given $(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc})$ -values, $n_{I(II)}(V_{oc})$ is determined.

Now, for $V_{oc} \geq V_{ocI1(ocII1)}$, one can propose the general expressions for the PVCF, in order to get exactly the values of $n_{I1(II1)}(V_{ocI1(ocII1)})$ and $n_{I2(II2)}(V_{ocI2(ocII2)})$, as functions of V_{oc} , by:

$$n_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc}) =$$

$$= n_{I1(II1)}(V_{ocI1(ocII1)}) + n_{I2(II2)}(V_{ocI2(ocII2)}) \times \left(\frac{V_{oc}}{V_{ocI1(ocII1)}} - 1 \right)^{\alpha(\beta)}, \quad (46)$$

where, for example, the values of $\alpha(\beta)$, obtained for $x = (0, 0.5 \text{ and } 1)$, will be reported in Tables 2.2 and 3.2 in Appendix 1, for $CdSe_{1-x}S_x$ alloy junctions, and in Tables 4.2 and 5.2 in Appendix 1, for $CdSe_{1-x}Te_x$, alloy junctions, respectively. One also notes that those $\alpha(\beta)$ -values depend on $(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x)$ -ones.

Tables 2.2 and 3.2, and Tables 4.2 and 5.2, in Appendix 1

So, one can determine the general expressions for the fill factors, as:

$$F_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc}) = \frac{X_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) - \ln[X_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) + b = 0.72]}{X_{I(II)}(V_{oc}) + a = 1}, \quad (47)$$

Finally, the efficiency $\eta_{I(II)}$ can be defined in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n) X(x)$ alloy-junction solar cells, by:

$$\eta_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, x, S; N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, x, V_{oc}) \equiv \frac{J_{scl(scII)} \times V_{oc} \times F_{I(II)}}{P_{in}}, \quad (48)$$

being assumed to be obtained at 1 sun illumination or at AM1.5G spectrum ($P_{in} = 0.100 \frac{W}{cm^2}$).

It should be noted that the maximal values of $\eta_{I(II)}$, $\eta_{I(II)max}$, are obtained at the corresponding ones of $V_{oc} = V_{ocI(ocII)}$, at which, $\left(\frac{\partial \eta_{I(II)}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, S, N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, V_{oc})}{\partial V_{oc}} \right)_{V_{oc}=V_{ocI(ocII)}} = 0$, as those given in next

Tables 2.2, 3.2, 4.2 and 5.2 in Appendix 1, being marked in bold. Further, from the well-known Carnot's theorem, being obtained by the second principle in thermodynamics, or by the entropy law, the maximum efficiency of a heat engine operating between hot (**H**) and cold (**C**) reservoirs is the ratio of the temperature difference between the reservoirs, $T_H - T_C$, to the H-reservoir temperature, T_H , expressed as:

$$\eta_{I(II)max}(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, S, N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, V_{ocI(ocII)}) = 1 - \frac{T_C = 300 \text{ K}}{T_H(W, N_{d(a)}, T, r_{d(a)}, S, N_{a(d)}, T, r_{a(d)}, V_{ocI(ocII)})}. \quad (49)$$

NUMERICAL RESULTS AND CONCLUDING REMARKS

We will respectively consider the two following cases of $n^+(p^+) - p(n) X(x) (\equiv CdSe_{1-x}S_x, CdSe_{1-x}Te_x)$ -junctions such as:

HD (Te; Sn) X(x) alloy ER – LD (In; Cd) X(x) – alloy BR – case, according to: 2 (n^+p) – junctions denoted by: (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd), and

HD (In; Cd) X(x) alloy ER – LD (Te; Sn) X(x) – alloy BR – case, according to: 2 (p^+n) – junctions denoted by: (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn).

Now, by using the physical conditions, given in Eq. (42), we can determine various following photovoltaic conversion coefficients.

(1)- $X(x) \equiv CdSe_{1-x}S_x$ – Alloy

Firs case: HD [Te; Sn] X(x) – Alloy ER – LD [In; Cd] X(x) – Alloy BR

Here, there are the 2 (n^+p) – $X(x)$ junctions, being denoted by: (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd).

Then, the numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{htt}^*}{\tau_{hE}}$, J_{Bpo} , J_{Eno} and J_{ol} , are calculated using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, and obtained, as those given in Table 2.1 in Appendix 1. Further, those of n_I , J_{scl} , F_I , η_I , and T_H , are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, and reported in the following Table 2.2 in Appendix 1.

Tables 2.1 and 2.2 in Appendix 1

Second case: HD [In; Cd] X(x) Alloy ER – LD [Te; Sn] X(x) Alloy BR

Here, there are 2 (p^+n) – $X(x)$ junctions, being denoted by: (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn).

Then, the numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}}$, J_{Bno} , J_{Epo} and J_{oll} , are calculated using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, and obtained, as those given in Table 3.1 in Appendix 1. Further, those of

n_{II} , J_{scII} , F_{II} , η_{II} , and T_H , are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, and reported in the following Table 3.2 in Appendix 1.

Tables 3.1 and 3.2 in Appendix 1

(2) $-X(x) \equiv CdSe_{1-x}Te_x - Alloy$

Firs case: HD [Te; Sn] X(x) Alloy ER – LD [In; Cd] X(x) Alloy BR

Here, there are the 2 (n^+p) – $X(x)$ junctions, being denoted by: (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd).

Then, from above physical conditions, given in Eq. (42), the numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{htt}^*}{\tau_{hE}}$, J_{Bpo} , J_{Eno} and J_{ol} , are calculated using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, and obtained, as those given in Table 4.1 in Appendix 1. Further, those of n_I , J_{scI} , F_I , η_I and T_H are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, and reported in the following Table 4.2 in Appendix 1.

Tables 4.1 and 4.2 in Appendix 1

Second case: HD [In; Cd] X(x) Alloy ER – LD [Te; Sn] X(x) Alloy BR

Here, there are 2 (p^+n) – $X(x)$ junctions, being denoted by: (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn).

Then, from above physical conditions, the numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}}$, J_{Bno} , J_{Epo} and J_{oII} , are calculated using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, and obtained, as those given in Table 5.1 in Appendix 1. Further, those of n_{II} , J_{scII} , F_{II} , η_I and T_H are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, and reported in the following Table 5.2 in Appendix 1.

Tables 5.1 and 5.2 in Appendix 1

Finally, some concluding remarks, obtained from those numerical results reported in above Tables 2.2, 3.2, 4.2 and 5.2, are discussed as follows.

(i)-As noted in Tables 2.1, 3.1, 4.1 and 5.1, the dark carrier-minority saturation current density $J_{ol(oII)}$ decreases slightly with increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -radius for given x , and decreases strongly with increasing x , for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius. Then, as remarked in Tables 2.2, 3.2, 4.2 and 5.2, at a same V_{oc} , the photovoltaic conversion factor, $n_{I(II)}(V_{oc})$, decreases slightly with increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -radius for given x , but it decreases strongly with increasing x , for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius. In other words, as discussed in Eq. (45), at a same V_{oc} , both $J_{ol(oII)}$ and $n_{I(II)}$ have the same variations for same physical conditions.

(ii)-With such variations of $n_{I(II)}(V_{oc})$, as observed in Tables 2.2, 3.2, 4.2 and 5.2, the maximal values of $\eta_{I(II)}$, $\eta_{I(II)max}$, and the corresponding ones of the H-reservoir temperature, T_H , are obtained at $V_{oc} = V_{ocI(ocII)}$, being marked in bold, increase with increasing x for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius.

(iii)-In particular, at $x=0$, both $n^+(p^+) - p(n) CdSe_{1-x}S_x(Te_x) [\equiv CdSe]$ alloys become the CdSe-crystals, as observed in Tables 1.1 and 1.2, and therefore, as given in Tables 2.2, 3.2, 4.2, and 5.2, we get the same numerical results of $\eta_{I max.(II max.)} [=28.184 \% (28.310 \%)]$.

(iv)-Further, at $x=1$ and for $Sn^+Cd (Cd^+Sn)$, we obtain: (a) in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n) CdSe_{1-x}S_x [\equiv CdS]$ alloy-junction solar cells, $\eta_{I max.(II max.)} = 34.375 \% (33.72 \%)$ and $T_H = 457.1 K (452.6 K)$, as those given in Tables 2.2 (3.2), and (b) in the $n^+(p^+) - p(n) CdSe_{1-x}Te_x [\equiv CdTe]$ alloy-junction solar cells, $\eta_{I max.(II max.)} = 25.676 \% (25.443 \%)$, according to: $T_H = 403.6 K (402.4 K)$, respectively, as those given in Tables 4.2 (5.2).

(v)-Finally, from above remarks (iii) and (iv), we can conclude that in order to obtain the highest efficiencies, the present ($CdSe_{1-x}S_x, CdSe_{1-x}Te_x$)- crystalline alloy junction solar cells could be chosen rather than the crystalline (CdSe, CdTe)-junction solar cells [1, 2], yielding the highest efficiencies equal to: 26.55 % and 23.69 %, respectively.

REFERENCES

1. H. Van Cong, "(26.55%, or 23.69%)- Limiting Highest Efficiencies, Obtained Respectively in $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ Crystalline ($X=CdTe$, or $CdSe$)-Junction Solar Cells at 300 K, Due to the Effects of Impurity Size, Temperature, Heavy Doping, and Photovoltaic Conversion," *Eur. J. Theor. Appl. Sci.*, vol. 1(5), pp. 249-268, 2023. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(5\).128](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(5).128)
 2. H. Van Cong, "(14.82%, 12.16%, 26.55%, or 23.69%)- Limiting Highest Efficiencies obtained in $n^+(p^+) - p(n)$ Crystalline ($X \equiv Ge, GaSb, CdTe, \text{ or } CdSe$)-Junction Solar Cells, Due to the Effects of Impurity Size, Temperature, Heavy Doping, and Photovoltaic Conversion," *SCIREA J. Phys.*, vol. 8, pp. 575-595, 2023.
 3. H. Van Cong, and G. Debiais, "A simple accurate expression of the reduced Fermi energy for any reduced carrier density," *J. Appl. Phys.*, vol. 73, pp. 1545-15463, 1993. DOI: [10.1063/1.353232](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.353232)
 4. H. Van Cong, and B. Doan Khanh, "Simple accurate general expression of the Fermi-Dirac integral $F_j(a)$ and for $j > -1$," *Solid-State Electron.*, vol. 35, pp. 949-951, 1992.
 5. H. Van Cong, "New series representation of Fermi-Dirac integral $F_j(-\infty < a < \infty)$ for arbitrary $j > -1$, and its effect on $F_j(a \geq 0_+)$ for integer $j \geq 0$," *Solid-State Electron.*, vol. 34, pp. 489-492, 1991.
 6. H. Van Cong et al., "Size effect on different impurity levels in semiconductors," *Solid State Communications*, vol. 49, pp. 697-699, 1984. DOI: [10.1016/0038-1098\(84\)90223-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0038-1098(84)90223-0)
 7. H. Van Cong, "Effects of impurity size and heavy doping on energy-band-structure parameters of various impurity-Si systems," *Physica B*, vol. 487, pp. 90-101, 2016. DOI: [10.1016/j.physb.2016.02.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physb.2016.02.006)
 8. H. Van Cong, and G. Debiais, "Energy band structure parameters and their data, derived from the measurements of minority carrier current density in heavily doped emitters of silicon devices," *Solar Ener. Mater. and Solar Cells*, vol. 45, pp. 385-399, 1997.
 9. H. Van Cong, "Apparent band-gap narrowing and its data derived from the measurements of minority-carrier current density in heavily doped emitters of silicon devices," *Physica Status Solidi A*, vol. 155, pp. 547-553, 1996. DOI: [10.1002/pssa.2211550229](https://doi.org/10.1002/pssa.2211550229)
 10. H. Van Cong, "A new solution for minority-carrier injection into the heavily doped emitter of silicon devices," *Physica Status Solidi A*, vol. 171, pp. 631-64, 1999. DOI: [10.1002/\(SICI\)1521-396X\(199902\)171:2%3C631::AID-PSSA631%3E3.0.CO;2-%23](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1521-396X(199902)171:2%3C631::AID-PSSA631%3E3.0.CO;2-%23)
- P. Singh & N. Ravindra, "Temperature dependence of solar cell performance-An analysis," *Solar Energy Materials and Solar Cells*, Vol. 101, pp. 36-45, 2012. DOI: [10.1016/j.solmat.2012.02.019](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2012.02.019)

APPENDIX 1

Table 1.1. From Equations (5, 8a, 8b, 9) and in the n(p)-type $CdSe_{1-x}S_x$ -alloy, the numerical results of the energy-band-structure parameters, reported below, suggest that, with increasing x and $r_{d(a)}$, both $B_{do(ao)}(x)$ and $\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)$ decrease, while the other ones increase

Donor		S	Se	Te	Sn
r_d (nm)	$\nearrow$	0.104	$r_{do}=\mathbf{0.114}$	0.132	0.140
x	$\nearrow$	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1
$B_{do}(x)$ in 10^8 (N/m ²)	$\nearrow$		3.71, 5.85, 8.54		
$\varepsilon(r_d, x)$	$\searrow$	10.56, 9.935, 9.314	10.2 , 9.6, 9	9.149, 8.611, 8.073	8.259, 7.773, 7.28
$E_d(r_d, x)$ meV	$\nearrow$	13.4, 21.1, 30.9	14.4, 22.7, 33.1	17.9, 28.2, 41.1	21.9, 34.5, 50.4
$E_{gn}(r_d, x)$ eV	$\nearrow$	1.839, 2.208, 2.577	1.84 , 2.21, 2.58	1.843, 2.215, 2.588	1.848, 2.222, 2.597
$E_{gin}(T = 300K, r_d, x)$ eV	$\nearrow$	1.739, 2.078, 2.418	1.74 , 2.08, 2.42	1.743, 2.085, 2.428	1.747, 2.092, 2.437 2.421
Acceptor		Ga	Mg	In	Cd
r_a (nm)	$\nearrow$	0.126	0.140	0.144	$r_{ao}=\mathbf{0.148}$
x	$\nearrow$	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1
$B_{ao}(x)$ in 10^8 (N/m ²)	$\nearrow$				6.94, 10.9, 15.87
$\varepsilon(r_a, x)$	$\searrow$	11.30, 10.63, 9.97	10.33, 9.72, 9.12	10.23, 9.631, 9.03	10.2 , 9.6, 9
$E_a(r_a, x)$ meV	$\nearrow$	47.9, 75.2, 109.6	57.3, 89.9, 131	58.4, 91.7, 133.6	58.8, 92.3, 134.5
$E_{gp}(r_a, x)$ eV	$\nearrow$	1.829, 2.193, 2.55	1.838, 2.207, 2.577	1.839, 2.209, 2.579	1.84 , 2.21, 2.58
$E_{gip}(T = 300K, r_a, x)$ eV	$\nearrow$	1.729, 2.063, 2.39	1.738, 2.077, 2.417	1.739, 2.079, 2.419	1.74 , 2.08, 2.42

Table 1.2. From Equations (5, 8a, 8b, 9) and in the n(p)-type $CdSe_{1-x}Te_x$ -alloy, the numerical results of the energy-band-structure parameters, reported below, suggest that, with increasing x and $r_{d(a)}$, both $B_{do(ao)}(x)$ and $\varepsilon(r_{d(a)}, x)$ decrease, while the other ones increase

Donor		S	Se	Te	Sn
r_d (nm)	$\nearrow$	0.104	$r_{do}=\mathbf{0.114}$	0.132	0.140
x	$\nearrow$	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1
$B_{do}(x)$ in 10^8 (N/m ²)	$\nearrow$		3.71, 3.42, 3.14		
$\varepsilon(r_d, x)$	$\searrow$	10.56, 10.61, 10.67	10.2 , 10.25, 10.31	9.149, 9.198, 9.25	8.26, 8.30, 8.30
$E_d(r_d, x)$ meV	$\nearrow$	13.4, 12.4, 11.3	14.4, 13.3, 12.2	17.9, 16.5, 15.1	21.9, 20.2, 20.2
$E_{gn}(r_d, x)$ eV	$\nearrow$	1.839, 1.729, 1.619	1.84 , 1.73, 1.62	1.843, 1.733, 1.623	1.848, 1.737, 1.735
$E_{gin}(T = 300K, r_d, x)$ eV	$\nearrow$	1.739, 1.599, 1.459	1.74 , 1.6, 1.46	1.743, 1.603, 1.463	1.747, 1.607, 1.604
Acceptor		Ga	Mg	In	Cd
r_a (nm)	$\nearrow$	0.126	0.140	0.144	$r_{ao}=\mathbf{0.148}$
x	$\nearrow$	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1	0, 0.5, 1
$B_{ao}(x)$ in 10^8 (N/m ²)	$\nearrow$				6.94, 9.69, 12.4
$\varepsilon(r_a, x)$	$\searrow$	11.30, 11.36, 11.42	10.33, 10.39, 10.44	10.23, 10.29, 10.34	10.2 , 10.255, 10.31
$E_a(r_a, x)$ meV	$\nearrow$	47.9, 66.9, 85.5	57.3, 80, 102.2	58.4, 81.6, 104.2	58.8, 82.1, 104.9
$E_{gp}(r_a, x)$ eV	$\nearrow$	1.829, 1.715, 1.601	1.838, 1.728, 1.617	1.839, 1.729, 1.619	1.84 , 1.73, 1.62
$E_{gip}(T = 300K, r_a, x)$ eV	$\nearrow$	1.729, 1.585, 1.441	1.738, 1.598, 1.457	1.739, 1.599, 1.459	1.74 , 1.6, 1.46

Table 2.1. In the HD [(Te; Sn)- CdSe_{1-x}S_x-alloy] ER-LD[(In; Cd)-CdSe_{1-x}S_x-alloy] BR, for physical conditions given in Eq. (42) and for a given x, our numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{htt}^*}{\tau_{hE}}$, J_{Bpo} , J_{Eno} and J_{ol} , are computed, using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, noting that J_{ol} decreases slightly with increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -radius for given x, but it increases strongly with increasing x for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius, being new results

n^+p		Te^+In	Sn^+Cd
Here, $\mathbf{x=0}$, and for the (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{htt}^*}{\tau_{hE}} = (0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bpo} in 10^{-24} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.0186	2.0120
J_{Eno} in 10^{-32} (A/cm ²)	↗	1.1672	1.2607
J_{ol} in 10^{-24} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.0186	2.0120
Here, $\mathbf{x=0.5}$, and for the (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{htt}^*}{\tau_{hE}} = (0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bpo} in 10^{-30} (A/cm ²)	↘	8.9610	8.9319
J_{Eno} in 10^{-35} (A/cm ²)	↘	6.8405	6.7214
J_{ol} in 10^{-30} (A/cm ²)	↘	8.9611	8.9320
Here, $\mathbf{x=1}$, and for the (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{htt}^*}{\tau_{hE}} = (0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bpo} in 10^{-35} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.9698	2.9602
J_{Eno} in 10^{-39} (A/cm ²)	↘	8.9851	7.5642
J_{ol} in 10^{-35} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.9707	2.9609

Table 2.2. In the HD [(Te; Sn)- CdSe_{1-x}S_x-alloy] ER-LD[(In; Cd)-CdSe_{1-x}S_x-alloy] BR, for physical conditions given in Eq. (42) and for a given x, our numerical results of n_i , J_{scl} , F_I , η_I , and T_H , are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, noting that both $\eta_{I_{max}}$ and T_H , marked in bold, increase with increasing x for given $r_{d(a)}$, being new results

$V_{oc}(V)$	n_i	$J_{scl}(\frac{mA}{cm^2})$	$F_I(\%)$	$\eta_I(\%)$
Here, $x=0$. For the (Te ⁺ In, Sn ⁺ Cd)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\alpha = 1.134$				
n^+p	Te ⁺ In; Sn ⁺ Cd			
0.73	0.5566; 0.5566	21.6; 21.6	90.45; 90.45	14.26; 14.26
0.811	0.6115; 0.6114	38.38; 38.38	90.53; 90.53	28.18; 28.18
0.812	0.6122; 0.6122	38.34; 38.34	90.53; 90.53	28.183; 28.184
$V_{ocI} = 0.812 V$				$T_H(K) = 417.7; 417.7$
0.813	0.6130; 0.6130	38.29; 38.29	90.53; 90.53	28.18; 28.18
0.8759	0.6635; 0.8128	30.19; 30.19	90.50; 90.53	23.93; 23.93
1	0.7714; 0.7714	12.03; 12.03	90.36; 90.36	10.87; 10.87
Here, $x=0.5$. For the (Te ⁺ In, Sn ⁺ Cd)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\alpha = 1.130$				
n^+p	Te ⁺ In; Sn ⁺ Cd			
0.73	0.4478; 0.4478	21.6; 21.6	91.95; 91.95	14.50; 14.50
0.805	0.4887; 0.4886	42.03; 42.03	92.02; 92.02	31.13; 31.13
0.806	0.4893; 0.4893	41.98; 41.98	92.02; 92.02	31.136; 31.137
$V_{ocI} = 0.806 V$				$T_H(K) = 435.6; 435.6$
0.807	0.4899; 0.4899	41.93; 41.93	92.02; 92.02	31.13; 31.13
0.8759	0.5345; 0.5344	30.25; 30.25	91.98; 91.98	24.38; 24.38
1	0.6215; 0.6215	9.525; 9.525	91.87; 91.87	8.750; 8.750
Here, $x=1$. For the (Te ⁺ In, Sn ⁺ Cd)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\alpha = 1.1272$				
n^+p	Te ⁺ In; Sn ⁺ Cd			
0.73	0.3732; 0.3731	21.6; 21.6	93.04; 93.04	14.67; 14.67
0.801	0.4054; 0.4054	46.09; 46.09	93.09; 93.09	34.371; 34.372
0.802	0.4059; 0.4059	46.04; 46.04	93.09; 93.09	34.374; 34.375
$V_{ocI} = 0.802 V$				$T_H(K) = 457.1; 457.1$
0.803	0.4064; 0.4064	45.98; 45.98	93.09; 93.09	34.372; 34.373
0.8759	0.4457; 0.4457	30.28; 30.28	93.06; 93.06	24.682; 24.682
1	0.5184; 0.5184	7.489; 7.489	92.96; 92.96	6.9616; 6.9613

Table 3.1. In the HD [(In; Cd)-CdSe_{1-x}S_x-alloy] ER-LD[(Te; Sn)-CdSe_{1-x}S_x-alloy] BR, for physical conditions given in Eq. (42) and for a given x, our numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}}$, J_{Bno} , J_{Epo} , and J_{oII} are computed, using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, noting that J_{oII} decreases slightly with increasing $r_{a(d)}$ -radius for given x, but it increases strongly with increasing x for given $r_{a(d)}$ -radius, being new results

p^n		In^+Te	Cd^+Sn
Here, $\mathbf{x=0}$, and for the (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}} = (0, 0)$, suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bno} in 10^{-25} (A/cm ²)	↘	7.6425	5.8970
J_{Epo} in 10^{-24} (A/cm ²)	↘	1.0791	1.0639
J_{oII} in 10^{-24} (A/cm ²)	↘	1.8433	1.6536
Here, $\mathbf{x=0.5}$, and for the (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}} = (0, 0)$, suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bno} in 10^{-30} (A/cm ²)	↘	3.7133	2.6178
J_{Epo} in 10^{-29} (A/cm ²)	↘	1.7733	1.7332
J_{oII} in 10^{-29} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.1447	1.9950
Here, $\mathbf{x=1}$, and for the (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}} = (0, 0)$, suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bno} in 10^{-35} (A/cm ²)	↘	1.3790	0.8676
J_{Epo} in 10^{-34} (A/cm ²)	↘	1.3943	1.3480
J_{oII} in 10^{-34} (A/cm ²)	↘	1.5322	1.4348

Table 3.2. In the HD [(In; Cd)-CdSe_{1-x}S_x-alloy] ER-LD[(Te; Sn)-CdSe_{1-x}S_x-alloy] BR, for physical conditions given in Eq. (42) and for a given x, our numerical results of n_{II} , J_{scII} , F_{II} , η_{II} , and T_H , are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, noting that both η_{IImax} . and T_H , marked in bold, increase with increasing x for given $r_{a(d)}$, being new results

$V_{oc}(V)$	n_{II}	$J_{scII}(\frac{mA}{cm^2})$	$F_{II}(\%)$	$\eta_{II}(\%)$
Here, $x=0$. For the (In ⁺ Te, Cd ⁺ Sn)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\beta = 1.1342$				
p^{+n}	In ⁺ Te; Cd ⁺ Sn			
0.73	0.5556; 0.5545	21.6; 21.6	90.46; 90.48	14.26; 14.27
0.811	0.6104; 0.6091	38.50; 38.54	90.54; 90.56	28.27; 28.31
0.812	0.6111; 0.6098	38.45; 38.50	90.54; 90.56	28.272; 28.310
$V_{ocII} = 0.812 V$				$T_H(K) = 418.2; 418.5$
0.813	0.6119; 0.6106	38.40; 38.45	90.54; 90.56	28.27; 28.308
0.8759	0.6623; 0.6609	30.29; 30.30	90.51; 90.53	24.01; 24.031
1	0.7700; 0.7684	12.05; 12.03	90.37; 90.39	10.89; 10.88
Here, $x=0.5$. For the (In ⁺ Te, Cd ⁺ Sn)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\beta = 1.1305$				
p^{+n}	In ⁺ Te; Cd ⁺ Sn			
0.73	0.4541; 0.4536	21.6; 21.6	91.86; 91.87	14.48; 14.49
0.806	0.4961; 0.4960	41.86; 41.89	91.93; 91.94	31.019; 31.04
0.807	0.4967; 0.4962	41.81; 41.84	91.93; 91.94	31.02; 31.045
$V_{ocII} = 0.807 V$				$T_H(K) = 434.9; 435.1$
0.808	0.4974; 0.4968	41.75; 41.79	91.93; 91.94	31.016; 31.041
0.8759	0.5419; 0.5413	30.38; 30.39	91.90; 91.90	24.46; 24.47
1	0.6302; 0.6294	9.729; 9.719	91.78; 91.78	8.929; 8.920
Here, $x=1$. For the (In ⁺ Te, Cd ⁺ Sn)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\beta = 1.127$				
p^{+n}	In ⁺ Te; Cd ⁺ Sn			
0.73	0.3814; 0.3811	21.6; 21.6	92.92; 92.92	14.65; 14.65
0.801	0.4144; 0.4140	45.24; 45.27	92.97; 92.98	33.692; 33.715
0.802	0.4149; 0.4149	45.19; 45.19	92.97; 92.97	33.70; 33.72
$V_{ocII} = 0.802 V$				$T_H(K) = 452.5; 452.6$
0.803	0.4154; 0.4154	45.13; 45.13	92.97; 92.97	33.69; 33.717
0.8759	0.4556; 0.4556	29.98; 29.98	92.94; 92.94	24.40; 24.41
1	0.5299; 0.5299	7.647; 7.647	92.84; 92.84	7.099; 7.092

Table 4.1. In the HD [(Te; Sn)-CdSe_{1-x}Te_x-alloy] ER-LD[(In; Cd)-CdSe_{1-x}Te_x-alloy] BR and for physical conditions given in Eq. (42) and for a given x, our numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{ht}^*}{\tau_{hE}}$, J_{Bpo} , J_{Eno} , and J_{ol} are computed, using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, noting that J_{ol} decreases slightly for given x with increasing $r_{d(a)}$ -radius for given x, but it increases strongly with increasing x for given $r_{d(a)}$ -radius, being new results

n^+p		Te^+In	Sn^+Cd
Here, $\mathbf{x=0}$, and for the (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{ht}^*}{\tau_{hE}} = (0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bpo} in 10^{-24} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.0186	2.0120
J_{Eno} in 10^{-32} (A/cm ²)	↘	1.1672	1.2607
J_{ol} in 10^{-24} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.0186	2.0120
Here, $\mathbf{x=0.5}$, and for the (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{ht}^*}{\tau_{hE}} = (0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bpo} in 10^{-22} (A/cm ²)	↘	6.9970	6.9743
J_{Eno} in 10^{-31} (A/cm ²)	↗	7.3846	8.2804
J_{ol} in 10^{-22} (A/cm ²)	↘	6.9970	6.9743
Here, $\mathbf{x=1}$, and for the (Te^+In, Sn^+Cd) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{ht}^*}{\tau_{hE}} = (0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bpo} in 10^{-19} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.1052	2.0984
J_{Eno} in 10^{-29} (A/cm ²)	↗	2.9601	3.4419
J_{ol} in 10^{-19} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.1052	2.0984

Table 4.2. In the HD [(Te; Sn)- CdSe_{1-x}Te_x-alloy] ER-LD[(In; Cd)-CdSe_{1-x}Te_x-alloy] BR, for physical conditions given in Eq. (42) and for a given x, our numerical results of n_I , J_{scI} , F_I , η_I , and T_H , are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, noting that both $\eta_{I_{max}}$ and T_H , marked in bold, increase with increasing x for given $r_{d(\alpha)}$, being new results

$V_{oc}(V)$	n_I	$J_{scI}(\frac{mA}{cm^2})$	$F_I(\%)$	$\eta_I(\%)$
Here, $\mathbf{x=0}$. For the (Te ⁺ In, Sn ⁺ Cd)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\alpha = 1.134$				
n^+p	Te ⁺ In; Sn ⁺ Cd			
0.73	0.5566; 0.5566	21.6; 21.6	90.45; 90.45	14.26; 14.26
0.811	0.6115; 0.6114	38.38; 38.38	90.53; 90.53	28.18; 28.18
0.812	0.6122; 0.6122	38.34; 38.34	90.53; 90.53	28.183; 28.184
$V_{ocI} = \mathbf{0.812 V}$				$T_H(K) = \mathbf{417.7; 417.7}$
0.813	0.6130; 0.6130	38.29; 38.29	90.53; 90.53	28.18; 28.18
0.8759	0.6635; 0.6635	30.19; 30.19	90.50; 90.50	23.93; 23.93
1	0.7714; 0.7714	30.19; 30.19	90.36; 90.36	10.87; 10.87
Here, $\mathbf{x=0.5}$. For the (Te ⁺ In, Sn ⁺ Cd)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\alpha = 1.1367$				
n^+p	Te ⁺ In; Sn ⁺ Cd			
0.73	0.6292; 0.6291	21.6; 21.6	89.49; 89.49	14.11; 14.11
0.815	0.6942; 0.6942	36.78; 36.78	89.59; 89.59	26.85; 26.85
0.816	0.6951; 0.6950	36.74; 36.74	89.59; 89.59	26.86; 26.86
$V_{ocI} = \mathbf{0.816 V}$				$T_H(K) = \mathbf{410.2; 410.2}$
0.817	0.6959; 0.6959	36.69; 36.69	89.59; 89.59	26.85; 26.85
0.8759	0.7493; 0.7493	30.17; 30.17	89.55; 89.55	23.66; 23.66
1	0.8711; 0.8710	13.45; 13.45	89.40; 89.41	12.02; 12.023
Here, $\mathbf{x=1}$. For the (Te ⁺ In, Sn ⁺ Cd)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\alpha = 1.1405$				
n^+p	Te ⁺ In; Sn ⁺ Cd			
0.73	0.7208; 0.7208	21.6; 21.6	88.33; 88.33	13.93; 13.93
0.820	0.7996; 0.7996	35.40; 35.40	88.44; 88.45	25.67; 25.67
0.821	0.8006; 0.8006	35.36; 35.36	88.44; 88.45	25.675; 25.676
$V_{ocI} = \mathbf{0.821 V}$				
0.822	0.8016; 0.8016	35.31; 35.31	88.44; 88.44	25.67; 25.67
0.8759	0.8575; 0.8575	30.26; 30.26	88.41; 88.41	23.43; 23.43
1	0.9966; 0.9966	15.05; 15.05	88.25; 88.25	13.28; 13.28

Table 5.1. In the HD [(In; Cd)- CdSe_{1-x}Te_x-alloy] ER-LD[(Te; Sn)-CdSe_{1-x}Te_x-alloy] BR, for physical conditions given in Eq. (42) and for a given x, our numerical results of $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}}$, J_{Bno} , J_{Epo} , and J_{oII} are computed, using Equations (38), (18), (36) and (41), respectively, noting that J_{oII} decreases slightly with increasing $r_{a(d)}$ -radius for given x, but it increases strongly with increasing x for given $r_{a(d)}$ -radius, being new results

p^n		In^+Te	Cd^+Sn
Here, $\mathbf{x=0}$, and for the (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}} = (0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bno} in 10^{-25} (A/cm ²)	↘	7.6425	5.8970
J_{Epo} in 10^{-24} (A/cm ²)	↘	1.0791	1.0639
J_{oII} in 10^{-24} (A/cm ²)	↘	1.8433	1.6536
Here, $\mathbf{x=0.5}$, and for the (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}} = (0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bno} in 10^{-22} (A/cm ²)	↘	2.6168	2.0441
J_{Epo} in 10^{-21} (A/cm ²)	↘	1.1608	1.1373
J_{oII} in 10^{-21} (A/cm ²)	↘	1.4224	1.3417
Here, $\mathbf{x=1}$, and for the (In^+Te, Cd^+Sn) -junctions and from Eq. (38), one obtains: $\frac{\tau_{ett}^*}{\tau_{eE}} = (0, 0)$ suggesting a completely transparent condition			
J_{Bno} in 10^{-20} (A/cm ²)	↘	7.7792	6.1501
J_{Epo} in 10^{-19} (A/cm ²)	↘	6.4975	6.3276
J_{oII} in 10^{-19} (A/cm ²)	↘	7.2754	6.9426

Table 5.2. In the HD [(In; Cd)-CdSe_{1-x}Te_x-alloy] ER-LD[(Te; Sn)-CdSeTe_x-alloy] BR, for physical conditions given in Eq. (42) and for a given x, our numerical results of n_{II} , J_{scII} , F_{II} , η_{II} , and T_H , are computed, using Equations (46, 45, 47, 48, 49), respectively, noting that both η_{IImax} and T_H , marked in bold, increase with increasing x for given $r_{a(d)}$, being new results

$V_{oc}(V)$	n_{II}	$J_{scII}(\frac{mA}{cm^2})$	$F_{II}(\%)$	$\eta_{II}(\%)$
Here, $x=0$. For the (In ⁺ Te, Cd ⁺ Sn)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\beta = 1.1342$				
p^{+n}	In ⁺ Te; Cd ⁺ Sn			
0.73	0.5556; 0.5545	21.6; 21.6	90.46; 90.48	14.26; 14.27
0.811	0.6104; 0.6091	38.50; 38.54	90.54; 90.56	28.27; 28.31
0.812	0.6111; 0.6098	38.45; 38.50	90.54; 90.56	28.272; 28.310
$V_{ocII} = 0.812 V$				$T_H(K) = 418.2; 418.5$
0.813	0.6119; 0.6106	38.40; 38.45	90.54; 90.56	28.27; 28.308
0.8759	0.6623; 0.6609	30.29; 30.30	90.51; 90.53	24.01; 24.031
1	0.7700; 0.7684	12.05; 12.03	90.37; 90.39	10.89; 10.88
Here, $x=0.5$. For the (In ⁺ Te, Cd ⁺ Sn)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\beta = 1.1375$				
p^{+n}	In ⁺ Te; Cd ⁺ Sn			
0.73	0.6393; 0.6384	21.6; 21.6	89.36; 89.37	14.09; 14.09
0.815	0.7052; 0.7043	36.75; 36.78	89.46; 89.47	26.79; 26.819
0.816	0.7061; 0.7052	36.71; 36.74	89.46; 89.47	26.80; 26.82
$V_{ocII} = 0.816 V$				$T_H(K) = 409.8; 409.9$
0.817	0.7070; 0.7061	36.67; 36.69	89.46; 89.47	26.80; 26.82
0.8759	0.7612; 0.7602	30.31; 30.32	89.43; 89.44	23.74; 23.75
1	0.8849; 0.8837	13.70; 13.69	89.28; 89.29	12.23; 12.22
Here, $x=1$. For the (In ⁺ Te, Cd ⁺ Sn)-junctions, the value of α given in Eq. (46) is: $\beta = 1.1415$				
p^{+n}	In ⁺ Te; Cd ⁺ Sn			
0.73	0.7444; 0.7435	21.6; 21.6	88.04; 88.05	13.88; 13.88
0.821	0.8266; 0.8256	35.13; 35.15	88.16; 88.17	25.424; 25.441
0.822	0.8276; 0.8266	35.08; 35.10	88.16; 88.17	25.425; 25.443
$V_{ocII} = 0.822 V$				$T_H(K) = 402.3; 402.4$
0.823	0.8287; 0.8277	35.04; 35.06	88.16; 88.17	25.424; 25.442
0.8759	0.8853; 0.8842	30.28; 30.29	88.12; 88.13	23.37; 23.386
1	1.0289; 1.0276	15.43; 15.42	87.96; 87.97	13.57; 13.56

